

GREAT Case Study GCS4

Rooftop Revolution

Work Package: WP4: GCS4 Case Study Rooftop Revolution

Grant Agreement Number: 101094766

Due date of deliverable: 2025

Actual completion date: January 2025

Start date of project: 01/02/2023 (36 months)

Dissemination Level: public (PU)

Deliverable Lead: FU

Author(s): Anna Merry (art.ma@frederick.ac.cy), Aravella Zachariou (aravella@cytanet.com.cy)

Point of Contact: Hendrik Drachsler (h.drachsler@dipf.de)

Deliverable Information

Reviewers	<Name> <E-mail>, <Name> <E-mail> & <Name> <E-mail>
Status	<input type="checkbox"/> Plan <input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input type="checkbox"/> Working <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Final <input type="checkbox"/> Approved
Abstract (for public dissemination only)	Click or tap here to enter text.
Keywords	Case Study, Games, Climate
Statement of originality	<p>This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise.</p> <p>Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both.</p>

Document History

Version	Date	Comment (Examples)
0.1	Click or tap to enter a date.	Draft 0.1 document created
0.2	31 January 2025	Final draft completed
0.3	Click or tap to enter a date.	Peer review and detailed feedback on overall structure and specific content
0.4	Click or tap to enter a date.	Integration of peer review comments and final editing
1.0	Click or tap to enter a date.	Document complete and submitted

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List of Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Confidential
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DI	Digital Innovation
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
EGE	The European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies
GREAT	Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
UKRI	United Kingdom Research & Innovation
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

This report is an overview of the case study ‘Rooftop Revolution’ (GCS4). ‘Rooftop Revolution’ is the fourth case study in the EU Horizon-funded project GREAT – Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation (<https://www.greatproject.gg/>). The case study centres around a co-designed serious game developed to be utilized as a facilitation tool between citizens and policy makers. Through learning and role-play scenarios, target groups were able to: voice their attitudes towards climate policies; gain valuable insights into specific initiatives; and enhance their acceptance of green infrastructure and sustainable urban planning.

‘Rooftop Revolution’ was implemented from October 2023 until December 2024 in Cyprus. The case study was led by an academic partner in the GREAT project, Frederick University and was sponsored by Urban Gorillas, an NGO active in urban regeneration and community engagement in transformations of public spaces. The study began as a pilot and was extended to a full case due to the strong interest from the case study sponsor. The case study engaged policy makers, architects, urban planners, design students, property owners and residents in a participatory process on the topic of greening privately multi-owned rooftops. The focus of the case study is a co-designed serious game developed in collaboration with Serious Games Interactive (SGI) partner in the GREAT project.

A series of 7 face to face serious dilemma games took place during the case study including 97 participants. The game was split into two parts: In part 1 players played themselves; and during part 2 they engaged in role-play. Participants explored: Benefits & Opportunities; Challenges & Barriers; Incentive Schemes and Fairness of Incentives. In-game data was collected via: participant voting and ranking; free text input; and word clouds, as well as voice recordings of the participants' discussions. Game play was further evaluated through participant debriefs, focus groups, expert interviews and feedback forms.

Results show that this innovative method of consultation allowed for the exchange of diverse opinions and constructive disagreements, enhancing realism in discussions and overall, participants positively evaluated their participation as they felt that the game sessions allowed for personal learning and perspective-taking. The usefulness of the GREAT methodology was confirmed by a request of a follow-up project by a local municipality, as well as the interest and request of urban design educators to utilise the serious dilemma game within their educational initiative.

Findings suggest that serious games can be a powerful tool for urban planning consultation as well as other policy areas related to climate change initiatives and policy areas, providing an interactive and engaging platform for policy discussion and community-driven solutions. The study underscores the potential of game-based learning in environmental policy development.

Conclusions of the case study and its success suggest that future research should explore scaling the methodology, adapting it for different urban challenges, and further evaluating its long-term impact on stakeholder decision-making and policy adoption.

2. Introduction

'Rooftop Revolution' (GCS4) is the fourth case study in the EU Horizon-funded project GREAT - Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation (<https://www.greatproject.gg/>). The case study was conducted in Cyprus, and was led by academics from Frederick University. 'Rooftop Revolution' began as a pilot study during cycle 1 of the GREAT project and was extended to a full case in cycle 2 due to the local situation in Cyprus and the strong interest from the case study sponsor Urban Gorillas.

Urban Gorillas is an NGO active in urban regeneration and community engagement in transformations of public spaces. Furthermore, Urban Gorillas are members of the European Creative Rooftop Network (ECRN), a network which spans nine European cities, promoting the creative use of rooftops to address urban challenges (a project co-funded by the CREATIVE EUROPE funding programme). As a result, Urban Gorillas identified rooftop utilization as a policy dilemma to be explored through the GREAT methodology, focusing on greening of multiple privately owned buildings roof spaces in Cyprus.

Placing the case study into context, the UN¹ has predicted that by 2050, 68% of the world's population will be living in cities. Demands on cities continue to grow, and globally, political decision-makers are in search of ways to tackle the climate crisis as well as challenges in climate resistance and energy consumption. According to the European Environment Agency² Europe is among the most forested regions of the world, around 40% of its land area is covered by forests. Yet, in 2021, the capital city of Nicosia, Cyprus had the lowest percentage of Urban Tree coverage in Europe at just 4%. Despite the low statistics, Cyprus continues to fill its empty plots within its cities with construction sites rather than green solutions. Between January 2022 and March 2023, over 160 new apartment buildings were initiated³ and between March 2023 and March 2024, this increased to 541, 165 specifically in Nicosia⁴.

¹ United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs. (2018). 2018 revision of world urbanization prospects. Retrieved from <https://www.un.org/development/desa/en/news/population/2018-revision-of-world-urbanization-prospects.html> (Accessed 30 May 2024)

² European Environment Agency. (2021). Forest dynamics in Europe and green infrastructure. Retrieved from <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/forest-dynamics-in-europe-and> (Accessed 15 January 2024)

³ Cyprus Business News. (2023). Of 160 new apartment buildings since January 2022, 40 in Limassol. Retrieved from <https://www.cbn.com.cy/article/2023/5/24/714236/of-160-new-apartment-buildings-since-january-2022-40-in-limassol/> (Accessed 15.5.24)

⁴ Incyprus. (2024). 541 apartment buildings under construction since 2023. Retrieved from <https://incyprus.philenews.com/insider/economy/541-apartment-buildings-under-construction-since-2023/#> (Accessed 15 November 2024)

A recent 2024 study by Adilkhanova et al. (2024) concluded from simulations that if implemented across cities as a 90% coverage, Green Roofs have the potential to lower energy consumption by 7.7% as well as lowering the temperature (air and surface) by 0.54 °C and 2.17 °C, respectively. Furthermore, green roofs can increase absorption of CO₂ and provide the added benefit of improved aesthetics of the city. In line with recent research and in response to the local declining situation in Cyprus regarding green open spaces, the initiative drew on local insights, including the first green roof pilot on a mixed-use building established by the Cyprus Energy Agency. This rooftop project set a precedent, illustrating the potential for widespread green roof adoption across urban centers like Nicosia.

Aligned with recent green roof developments both locally and globally, alongside advocacy efforts from the Cyprus Environmental Commissioner and the Ministry of Agriculture, the case study aimed to produce actionable insights into the social acceptance of green roofs allowing target groups (citizens/architects/urban planners/investors) to voice their attitudes towards climate policies; gain valuable insights into specific initiatives; and enhance their acceptance of green infrastructure and sustainable urban planning, whilst at the same time fostering a two-way knowledge transfer between participants and policymakers. Findings aimed to be transferred to the case study sponsor Urban Gorillas in the form of an actionable insights document, which could be disseminated and communicated to local municipalities, policymakers and Urban planners for future green infrastructure planning.

The key objectives of this case study were:

- What are the responses of stakeholders for an initiative promoting the greening of privately multi owned rooftops?
- What incentives would be effective in promoting an initiative for the greening of privately multi owned rooftops?
- How can fairness be achieved through incentives initiative for the greening of privately multi owned rooftops?

3. Methodology

'Rooftops Revolution' aimed to evaluate how effective are games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas. More specifically it aimed to demonstrate that the games-based methodology effectively: engaged participants; fostered meaningful dialogue and collaboration; enhanced understanding of rooftop utilization's potential for sustainability; and increased citizen participation in urban planning discussions. Furthermore resulting in transferable actionable insights for Urban Gorillas. The overarching GREAT research questions addressed through GCS4 were:

- RQ1.1: Which games-based activities can be used to elicit, represent and communicate citizens' views on social dilemmas?
- RQ1.2: How effective are games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas?
- RQ1.3: How efficient is the use of games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas?
- RQ2.1: What are the affordances of games in eliciting and representing citizens' views in relation to social dilemmas.

The study employed a variety of mixed methods allowing the case study lead to employ both qualitative and quantitative methodologies to triangulate the research findings. Overall the Research Design was based upon the GREAT projects eight step case study cycle (see detailed breakdown below). These methods included: collaborative online workshops; expert interviews; focus groups; feedback questionnaires; and participant debriefs. The central data collection instrument was the serious dilemma game 'Rooftops Reimagined', produced by project Partner Serious Games Interactive (SGI), Denmark.

Within the 'Rooftop Revolution' case study the DiBL approach was chosen based on three key factors:

- Multiplayer dilemma based solution
- Quantitative & Qualitative Research Style
- Ability to promote in-depth Exploration & Discussion

In order to develop the game multiple meetings took place with Urban Gorillas as well as the Cyprus Energy Agency in order to, describe the dilemma in sufficient detail; provide real world scenarios to create compelling situations for the participants in the game; decide on the interactions that occur during the game; determine how and provide resources about the dilemma (e.g. text descriptions, photos, web links, videos).

The dilemma game design was created by the case study lead, and a member of the SGI technical team, who acted in a consulting role. All requirements had been gathered from the UG team, and the case study lead then took responsibility for the design. For the DiBL game a minimum of 8 participants was necessary for an effective session to be delivered, with a maximum of 50 participants if conducted online.

Once piloted and refined, a series of 7 face to face serious dilemma games took place during the case study including 97 participants. The game was split into two parts: during part 1, players played themselves, while in part 2 participants assumed roles opposite to themselves, thus they engaged in role-play activities. Participants explored: Benefits & Opportunities; Challenges & Barriers; Incentive Schemes and Fairness of Incentives. In both instances

participants are asked to: engage in discussions to determine their key priorities and concerns. They present their arguments to the group and in turn attempt to convince one another of their preferred incentives. Participants were reminded that to achieve a mutually beneficial outcome, they must consider the views of others. Within the game itself data was collected via: participant voting and ranking; free text input; and word clouds, as well as voice recordings of the participants' discussions. Evaluation data collection methods included: Evaluation of transcript discussions during Game Play; Participant Debrief; Feedback Questionnaire; Focus group; and Interviews with key stakeholders.

3.2 Participant selection

Participant selection for the case study in Cyprus began through an existing relationship between the Spatial Design and Artefact Research Unit of Frederick University and Urban Gorillas NGO. Urban Gorillas are a multi-disciplinary team of creative urbanites united by their common vision and enthusiasm for constantly improving life in the city. Their team has a vivid interest to transform public spaces into lively, innovative and inclusive hubs, to cultivate civil society and to impact policies. Involved in initiatives related to climate change initiatives in the urban context, Urban Gorillas are committed to urban sustainability within the context of the New European Bauhaus. Furthermore, Urban Gorillas are members of the European Creative Rooftop Network (ECRN), a network which spans nine European cities, promoting the creative use of rooftops to address urban challenges (a project co-funded by the CREATIVE EUROPE funding programme).

The case study lead at Frederick University presented the GREAT project to Urban Gorillas and discussed the innovative means that the project could achieve in relation to investigating the potential of digital games and gameplay to engage citizens to provide input into developing policy priorities on climate change. Furthermore, pointing out that this method would allow citizens to express preferences and attitudes on policy dilemmas related to climate change. As a result, Urban Gorillas identified rooftop utilization as a policy dilemma to be explored through the GREAT methodology, focusing on Greening of multiple private owned buildings roof spaces in Cyprus.

Both Urban Gorillas and Frederick University promoted the 'Rooftop Revolution' game sessions in May 2024 with the main sessions taking place in June 2024. The primary means was through social media where participants completed a registration form or expression of interest.

Overview of DiBL participants:

Total Participants: 97 Participants

Total Game Sessions: 7

Age Range: 18 - 75 Years (18 - 35 years is the most frequent category)

72% Female/ 28% Male

Game session length: Part 1 80 mins/Part 2 60 mins

Participants of the game were invited to participate in a follow up focus group to evaluate the serious dilemma game via private email. Only participants who selected their future interest in the case study were contacted and invited to an online zoom session. Expert interview participants included 2 Urban planning experts, both from the Nicosia town planning board active in Urban planning and Urban planning consultation, as well as a representative of both Urban Gorillas and the Cyprus Energy Agency. Participants were selected due to their extensive knowledge in both current consultation measures and knowledge in Green Roof implementation within the Cypriot context.

3.3 Ethical Considerations

Before any data collection took place, ethical approval was obtained from the Cyprus National Ethics Agency. Prior to participating in any sessions, individuals were introduced to the GREAT project and provided with a consent form to review and sign, confirming their voluntary participation. This process ensured that all participants were fully aware of the study's objectives and their rights. Data collection was carried out using participants' personal mobile devices, tablets, or laptops. To maintain privacy and confidentiality, all collected data were anonymized, with no identifying information retained. This approach upheld ethical standards and safeguarded participant confidentiality throughout the study.

3.4 Mapping of RQ's to Case Study:

Table 1. Mapping of research questions to the case study

Revised research objectives and questions	<i>Simple formulation in terms of GREAT</i>	Yes/No
RQ1. To understand how games-based activities can be designed to provide a link between citizens and policy makers.		
RQ1.1 Which games-based activities can be used to elicit, represent and communicate citizens' views on social dilemmas?	<i>How can GREAT be achieved?</i>	YES

RQ1.2 How effective are games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas?	<i>Does GREAT do what we want it to do?</i>	YES
RQ1.3 How efficient is the use of games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas?	<i>How much work is it to use the GREAT approach?</i>	YES
RQ1.4 How widely applicable are games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas, and which variables need to be taken into consideration when adapting them to different contexts?	<i>How widely applicable is what we do?</i>	NO
RQ2. To understand the benefits and risks to citizens, policy stakeholders and policy makers, of using games-based activities as a link between citizens and policy makers.		
RQ2.1 What are the affordances of games in eliciting and representing citizens' views in relation to social dilemmas.	<i>What is it about GREAT that makes it good for gathering and representing opinions and attitudes?</i>	YES
RQ2.2 What are the benefits and risks to policy makers and policy stakeholders of using games-based activities to elicit, represent and communicate citizens' views on social dilemmas?	<i>What is good and bad about GREAT for policy stakeholders and policy makers?</i>	NO
RQ2.3 What are the benefits and risks to citizens of using games-based activities to elicit, represent and communicate their views on social dilemmas?	<i>What is good and bad about GREAT for citizens?</i>	NO

3.5 Detail the design process for the case study:

The ‘Rooftop Revolution’ case study design followed the GREAT projects case study cycle as seen in figures 1 and 2. The project objectives and steps in the cycle determined the types of activities and participants to be involved in the co-design processes, i.e. citizens, domain experts, policy stakeholders and policymakers etc. The following section outlines the steps of the methodology in relation to the ‘Rooftop Revolution’ case study.

Figure 1. GREAT Case Study Cycle

Figure 2. GREAT Case Study Cycle (Partners)

Table 2. Detailing the design process for the case study

Step of Case Study Cycle	Overview of the Eight-Step Cycle
<p>Create and Prioritise Research Topics (Step 1)</p> <p><i>Document the outcomes of initial workshops.</i></p>	<p><i>Provide a brief description of each step in the case study process.</i></p> <p>Objectives: Create and prioritise research topics/ What the case study will achieve and with who?</p> <p>Expected Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - List of current, relevant dilemmas - Expected insight and evidence - Indicators of attitudes and preferences - Stakeholders to be engaged with <p>Stage 1 Activities:</p> <p>The activity consisted of two phone meetings of one hour each, the academic lead of Frederick University and a board member of Urban Gorillas. The first meeting presented the GREAT project and Urban Gorillas and explored the potential for collaboration. The second meeting discussed possible themes which could serve as the basis of a dilemma game.</p> <p>The discussion consisted of relevant dilemmas which were appropriate to UG as well as suitable pilot studies for GREAT. Initially the conversation centred around the 15-minute city concept and the issues currently facing Cyprus in relation to travel and moving towards sustainable movement in the city as this was a suggestion by Frederick University based on current research. During the conversation UG brought up the issue of repurposing rooftops as a way to provide multiple spaces in the City.</p> <p>The following dilemmas were brought forward:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Use of alternate vehicles ● Upgrading the park and ride schemes ● Incentives for alternative methods of travel ● Urban planning upgrades, greening and improvements ● Use of public/large buildings roof spaces as social spaces ● Greening of multiple private owned buildings roof spaces ● Water management/collection on private owned buildings roof spaces <p>Three options were selected for further consideration, all of which were related to roof spaces.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Use of public/large buildings roof spaces as social spaces

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Greening of multiple private owned buildings roof spaces ● Water management/collection on private owned buildings roof spaces <p>Follow up discussions after the meeting led to Urban Gorillas committing to the design of a DiBL game.</p>
<p>Collaborate in Study Design (Step 2)</p> <p><i>Describe the collaborative case study design process.</i></p>	<p>Objectives: Collaborate in study design/ Game activity concepts</p> <p>Expected Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scenario to elicit required insight - Identify activities to be designed - Thematic content that is needed - Data to be gathered and pipeline - Timeframe for implementation <p>Stage 2 Activities:</p> <p>The main content of the meeting was:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● UG identification of a policy action/dilemma related to the Climate Emergency which they would like to test amongst a specific group, and explanation of the reasons why this policy action/dilemma was chosen. ● UGs introduced the concept of rooftops and the projects they have been doing so far ● UG described how the use of rooftops can be related to climate change and how the repurposing of rooftops can work towards climate neutrality ● Discussion of the specific policy relating to rooftops or the overall concepts that we would like to (and can) test amongst groups of participants ● Who the groups of participants should be (citizens/building owners etc) ● What could usefully be done with the results ● Discussion of desired outcomes for UG. <p>During the activity the participants had access to the DiBL platform and were shown a 'test' game by the case study lead in order to fully understand the potentials of DiBL. Towards the end of the meeting it was decided that the specific issue to concentrate on in relation to the general theme of rooftops should be the greening of privately multi owned rooftops and the incentives that could be offered to citizens. Although greening of the rooftops is directly linked to the climate emergency there are also additional benefits to the action.</p>

	<p>Multiple potential groups were identified for participation in the DiBL game:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Homeowners ● Building Developers ● Management companies ● Architects ● People who rent accommodation ● Neighbours ● Potential buyers <p>An important issue moving forward with the DiBL pilot was to finalise choice of participants</p>
<p>Collaborate in Design of Games-Based Activities (Step 3)</p> <p><i>Explain the collaborative design of game activities.</i></p>	<p>Objectives: Collaborate in game design</p> <p>Expected Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaborative design of game activities - Co-create story and narrative and/or quiz game - Specify the detail of the dilemma scenario and/or quiz game - Design interactions and deployment of content <p>Stage 3 of the case study cycle also examined how a GREAT case study facilitator could take on a consulting role in the creation of a DiBL game, i.e. that the sponsors provide input, but the facilitation team completes the hands-on design work.</p> <p>Stage 3a Activities:</p> <p>Multiple meetings took place with Urban Gorillas as well as the Cyprus Energy Agency in order to, describe the dilemma in sufficient detail; provide real world scenarios to create compelling situations for the participants in the game; decide on the interactions that occur during the game; determine how and provide resources about the dilemma (e.g. text descriptions, photos, web links, videos).</p> <p>The dilemma game design was created by the academic lead at Frederick University, and a member of the SGI technical team, who acted in what may be termed a ‘consulting’ role, in the sense that they had gathered requirements from the UG team, and then took responsibility for the design.</p> <p>Stage 3 b Activities:</p> <p>The main objective during stage 3b was to produce a pilot DiBL game to be internally tested. The activity included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Developing the content for the DiBL wireframe. All questions and dilemmas were refined ● Transferring the knowledge gained from UG to SGI (DiBL creators) for the development of the game pilot.

	<p>This stage consisted of dialogue between the case study facilitator (who developed a good understanding of the dilemma and the objectives of the sponsor, and also has a good understanding of the DiBL platform) and a member of the SGI team (who can guided the facilitator through the detail of the design process, and provide guidance on effective designs).</p>
<p>Piloting and Gathering Data (Step 4) - PILOT & TEST <i>Document the piloting phase and data collection.</i></p>	<p>Objectives: Piloting and Gathering Data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Games activities with case study participants - Dilemma games with chosen focus group participants <p>Stage 4a Activities:</p> <p>The activity focused on the pilot of the dilemma game built in DiBL through steps 1-3. It consisted of a dialogue between the pilot facilitator (who had developed a good understanding of the dilemma and the objectives of the sponsor, and also had a good understanding of the DiBL platform) and the invited participants. The activity utilised the following steps prior to the pilot:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Invite participants through Frederick University Contacts 2. Set a date and Time for the pilot session <p>The activity utilised the following steps during the pilot:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Present the informed consent form to the participants 2. Introduce the facilitator 3. Set up the DiBL game through participants mobile devices 4. Record the session via audio (ensure the consent form has been signed by all participants prior to recording) 4. Play part 1 of the game 5. Arrange snack and beverages for participants 6. Play part 2 of the game (roleplay) 7. Include short feedback questions 8. Present the google form for further feedback <p>During stage 4a, a fully playable DiBL Dilemma game was produced and tested. Pilot player concerns were addressed by SGI in order to understand if some are technically viable. Although the activity was a pilot the insights for the policy dilemma were well balanced, positive and constructive. Results may be able to be added to the policy insight at later stages in the cycle. Finally, the pilot testing to an audience of diverse participants allowed the facilitator to test her facilitation skills and to learn from her experience, before implementing</p>

further sessions. The pilot in step 4a provided implications for step 4b:

- Refine the DiBL game based on participants comments
- Produce a second version of the game directed at Architects, Designers and Engineers
- Produce invitations via social media and email for stakeholders
- Implement further game sessions.

A number of positives such as: Assigning Stakeholder roles; facilitated group decisions; negotiation and consensus building; debriefing and reflection; and visual aids and props worked well. Whereas difficulties such as Clarity of roles; complexity of the scenarios; technological challenges and gathering enough people at the same place and time were challenged to overcome in step 4b.

Feedback suggested that the interactive, role-playing format was engaging, but some refinements to the presentation and flow of information could help enhance the experience and outcomes. These suggestions were transferred to SGI and Urban Gorillas for game refinement.

The greatest observation from the case study lead was the content, data and outcomes provided from the pilot study was more than expected. In essence the sessions engaging qualities elicited opinions and insights far beyond the expectations of a traditional consultation. This reflection is vitally important to the overarching research question of the GREAT project: How effective are games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas?

Stage 4b Activities:

Once piloted and refined through a series of back and forth meetings between the case study lead, Urban Gorillas and SGI, a series of 7 face to face serious dilemma games took place during the case study including 97 participants. The game was played in two parts: during part 1, players played themselves, while in part 2 participants assumed roles opposite to themselves, thus they engaged in role-play activities. Participants explored: Benefits & Opportunities;

	<p>Challenges & Barriers; Incentive Schemes and Fairness of Incentives. In both instances participants are asked to: engage in discussions to determine their key priorities and concerns. They present their arguments to the group and in turn attempt to convince one another of their preferred incentives. Participants were reminded that to achieve a mutually beneficial outcome, they must consider the views of others. Within the game itself data was collected via: participant voting and ranking; free text input; and word clouds, as well as voice recordings of the participants' discussions. Post game a short debrief took place and participants filled in a feedback form, providing data to support the in game data.</p>
<p>Data Interpretation and Outcomes (Step 5) <i>Analyse and interpret the data collected.</i></p>	<p>Objectives: Data interpretation and outcomes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaborative data analysis - Interpretation of the data obtained from games activities - Assessment of the value of the data and possible need for further data collection <p>Stage 5 Activities:</p> <p>In order to Interpret the Data finding of the DiBL sessions the case study lead from Frederick University conducted a series of interviews and a focus group in order to discuss the data with policy stakeholders and the participants themselves as well as to gain feedback on the DiBL approach for future improvements.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Interview 1 & 2: 2 Urban Planners - Members of the Nicosia Town Planning Board 2. Interview 3: Member of Urban Gorillas & the Cyprus Energy Agency 3. Focus Group: 9 participants from the DiBL sessions who volunteered to be part of a post session focus group <p>The three activities aimed to assess the data gained from the DiBL sessions.</p> <p>Interview 1 highlighted the need for a more strategic, city-wide approach to green roof implementation in Nicosia, rather than relying on scattered, individual efforts. Proposing zoning specific areas between parks where all flat-roof buildings would be required to incorporate green roofs, creating interconnected green corridors that enhance biodiversity and environmental sustainability. Rather than focusing solely on the energy efficiency of individual buildings, he emphasized the broader ecological and social benefits of a coordinated</p>

green infrastructure. This discussion played a key role in interpreting the data gathered from the games-based activities, assessing the value of the findings, and identifying potential gaps for further data collection. Byron's contributions reinforced the need for a collaborative, well-planned strategy that integrates multiple urban sustainability goals while maintaining practical feasibility.

Interview 2 highlighted the importance of using innovative consultation tools, such as the game methodology, to engage diverse stakeholders in discussions on green roofs and urban sustainability. Aligning with Interview 1, it emphasized that addressing rooftop challenges—such as limited space for PV panels and green systems—requires creative solutions, including utilizing building facades or integrating advanced technologies like transparent PV panels. A key concern raised was the risk of greenwashing, stressing the need to focus on measurable impacts, such as energy savings and biodiversity improvements, to justify investments in green roofs. Additionally, the game methodology was recognized as a powerful tool for engaging students and the public, fostering early awareness and participation in sustainable urban planning. While acknowledging challenges such as the resource-intensive nature of the game and the complexities of group dynamics, the interview underscored its value in generating both qualitative and quantitative insights to support informed policymaking. The discussion reinforced the need for well-maintained green roofs, backed by strong policies and stakeholder collaboration, to ensure long-term sustainability and maximize city-wide environmental benefits.

Interview 3 emphasized the importance of community involvement and game-based approaches in engaging diverse perspectives on climate change initiatives. Key challenges, such as structural integrity, rainwater collection, and rooftop design management, were explored alongside potential solutions. The discussion also highlighted how interactive methods can facilitate social change by making education more engaging and accessible. The interviewee expressed strong support for the game-based approach, particularly valuing the role-playing element in fostering empathy and deeper understanding of the complexities of green roof implementation. While acknowledging technical and structural

	<p>concerns raised by participants, these were seen as challenges to be addressed rather than obstacles to adoption. Creative solutions proposed by participants, such as using condensation and air conditioning runoff for irrigation, were noted as promising ideas. Regarding the game itself, the interviewee recognized its effectiveness in community engagement but acknowledged the significant time and expertise required for its development and facilitation. A recommendation was made to run the game over multiple sessions rather than a single event, allowing participants to refine their perspectives. Additionally, the game was seen as an equalizing tool that could engage stakeholders at different levels more effectively. The interview also highlighted the real-world impact of the Cyprus Energy Agency’s green roof pilot project, which provided tangible evidence of green roof viability in the local climate. This real-world example complemented the game discussions, reinforcing the potential for well-designed and maintained green roofs.</p> <p>The focus group focused on feedback from participants on the game sessions rooftop reimagined which was designed to simulate the implementation of green roofs in Cyprus. Participants found the game straightforward with guidance but noted that without expert assistance, the game might have been confusing. The game facilitated diverse opinions and constructive disagreements, enhancing realism. Key issues discussed included the need for better building management, the importance of accessibility, and the challenges of maintenance and financial constraints. It also allowed the case study lead to gain insights into why certain answers were received. Suggestions to improve the game included using real-life testimonials, providing data to architects, and considering legislative changes. The meeting concluded with suggestions to develop an insight report, case studies, and a collaborative platform to promote green roof initiatives.</p>
<p>Conclusions and Outputs (Step 6) <i>Summarise conclusions and recommendations.</i></p>	<p>Objectives: Conclusions and outputs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy conclusions & evaluation - Collaborative formulation of case-study conclusions - Evaluation of the effectiveness of the method <p>Stage 6 Activities:</p> <p>The objective of stage 6 was the conclusions and recommendations which would be transferred to Urban</p>

	<p>Gorillas as actionable policy insights. The quantitative and qualitative data collected through: Game data; transcripts; participant debrief; participant feedback questionnaires; interviews; and focus group were summarized, concluded and consolidated into an actionable insights report in a powerpoint format. The key outcomes were the actionable insights and recommendations to be transferred to step 7 for the dissemination of outcomes and public engagement, through both academic publications and presentations as well as a multi stakeholder event.</p>
<p>Public Engagement and Dissemination of Outcomes (Step 7) <i>Outline strategies for disseminating findings.</i></p>	<p>Objectives: Public engagement, disseminate outcomes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community engagement - Dissemination of case study outcomes (e.g. in web posts, events, presentations, webinars and social networks) <p>Stage 7 Activities: A variety of Dissemination actions took place in order to disseminate results of the ‘Rooftop Revolution’ case study.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Changing Cities Conference: At the International Conference on Changing Cities VI in Rhodes, Greece, in June 2024, Dr. Anna Merry from Frederick University and Marina Kyriakou from Urban Gorillas, presented the initial stages of the ‘Green Roofs’ case study. The presentation emphasized the potential of games to bridge the gap between public opinion and policy making, especially in the context of pressing challenges like climate change. By promoting dialogue and creating a space for diverse perspectives, the "Rooftop Revolution" game offers a unique way to reimagine urban spaces for sustainability. The Extended Abstract can be found here: https://zenodo.org/records/13124481 2. EU-CONEXUS EENVIRO Research Conference: At the Eenviro conference in Bucharest, Romania, October 2024, Anna Merry & Aravella Zachariou from Frederick University and Jane Yau from DIPF Leibniz Institute for Research and Information in Education, presented a poster entitled: ‘Exploring dilemma games in sustainable urban planning: a Cypriot case study on urban rooftop utilization for climate change’. The event allowed for engaging in-depth discussions on the case study content and the request for further information and a ‘playable’ game to be utilised as a learning resource in higher education Urban Planning. The Poster can be found here: https://zenodo.org/records/14036816

	<p>The full paper can be found here: https://zenodo.org/records/14771671</p> <p>3. Dissemination event on the Cyprus Energy Agency green rooftop: Taking the case study almost full circle, the event gathered together over 30 participants on the green roof which inspired the 'Rooftop Revolution Case Study'. Participants included Academics, Urban Planners, Members of the Cyprus Energy Agency, Design and Urban Planning students, Members of the Nicosia Municipality and Ministry of Agriculture. During the event case study results were discussed and participants were able to play a shortened version of the DiBL game.</p>
<p>Advocate for Change at Policy Level (Step 8)</p> <p><i>Document advocacy efforts undertaken.</i></p>	<p>Objectives: Advocate for change at policy level</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy stakeholder engagement: - Distribute insight report on climate emergency dilemmas - Present results to policy makers - Dialogue with dilemma stakeholders, as required <p>Stage 8 Activities:</p> <p>A powerpoint presentation was created as an insights report to be presented to policy makers and the case study sponsor Urban Gorillas. The insights document included key actionable insights. Insights suggested a variety of future actions such as changes to the building management structure in Cyprus and the need for flexible policy implementation based on the socio-economic groups living in a building. The case study outcomes suggest that in order to successfully implement a green roof policy there are multiple steps required beforehand. First a meeting with Urban Gorillas took place, this was an online meeting where the insights were discussed as well as future directions of the study. The conclusions of the meeting were to produce an online PDF version of the insights document for onward dissemination. This document is in progress and will be concluded by the end of February 2025. Secondly 3 members of Frederick University met with the Mayor and other representatives of the newly formed Municipality of South Nicosia. The meeting resulted in the request of a follow up case study based on the successful findings of 'Rooftop Revolution.'</p>

4. SWOT Analysis of Case Study Methodology:

Table 3. SWOT analysis of the case study methodology

Strengths <i>Examine the strengths of the case study methodology, such as the use of innovative data collection techniques (e.g., game-based activities, surveys) or high participant engagement levels.</i>	Weaknesses <i>Identify any methodological limitations encountered, such as sample size constraints or challenges in capturing a full range of participant perspectives.</i>
<p>Engagement & Participation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The game-based approach encouraged active participation from a diverse group of stakeholders, including policymakers, students, architects, and residents. • The games based activities engaged a variety of stakeholders who some of which would not have usually been involved in urban planning consultation or policy discourse. <p>Policy Stakeholder Collaboration:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Urban Gorillas Provided a real-world dilemma for actionable insights • The case study included an organisation which had a clear point of view for a policy dilemma and whom were engaged in the data interpretation <p>Further Stakeholder Engagement: Participation of further policy stakeholders (Cyprus Energy Agency and the Municipality of South Nicosia) in the dissemination of the results</p> <p>Innovative Games Based Data Collection Methodology: There was a variety of input methods in the DiBL approach: Free Text/Multiple Choice/Word Clouds/ Hierarchy/ Voting</p> <p>Method of Delivery: The face to face nature of the game play allowed for the facilitator to not merely run the session but to provide further explanations when required</p>	<p>Mode of Delivery and Sample Size: Engaging a great number of persons in one place at the same time in a face-to-face manner is a challenging task. As a result less persons than those who signed up to participate could attend the planned sessions.</p> <p>Preparation and Resource Intensity: The case study preparation required significant preparation, facilitator training and structured materials and resources. This resulted in time delays to the initial case study timeline.</p> <p>Participant Knowledge Gaps: The varied prior knowledge on the knowledge of urban sustainability, climate change, and green roofs affected the depth of discussion in some instances, with participants relying on the facilitator to answer specialised questions on the subject</p> <p>Participant Diversity: Participants engaged in the game sessions through open calls, as such this may have excluded some groups from engaging in the sessions. ie. low income, marginalised, those with limited knowledge and access to technology</p> <p>Time Constraints and Pressure: Conducting the sessions within a tight time period before the mediterranean summer break put pressure on the game sessions. Furthermore the 2 game sessions lasted 3 hours, which limits participants time they have free in a day to participate in such initiatives.</p>

<p>Multimethod approach to Evaluation: The variety of data collection and evaluation methods allowed for the triangulation of research findings</p> <p>Perspective-Taking & Empathy: Role-playing allowed participants to step into different roles, fostering a deeper understanding of diverse viewpoints.</p> <p>Structured yet Flexible Problem-Solving: The methodology combined structured decision-making with creativity, allowing for realistic policy discussions.</p> <p>Bridging Gaps: Rooftop Revolution provided a novel platform for communication between citizens and policymakers, enhancing transparency and inclusive decision-making.</p> <p>Educational Value: The game facilitated learning by making complex urban sustainability issues more accessible and engaging.</p>	<p>Technological Limitations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limitations in the DiBL 1.0 platform were unable to adjust some visuals and bugs in the original pilot game. Participants made valid observations which were transferred to the game developer, yet limitations of the DiBL platform could not amend the suggestions. • Furthermore during game play ‘bugs’ in the game meant that some players could not answer specific questions, some were ‘thrown out’ of the game and in one instance participants could not answer correctly as they could not insert ‘spaces’ between words. These technical hitches could have misconstrued the final answers of some participants. <p>Output of DiBL Data: The outputs in both the final PDF Reports and Excel files were not structured as well as required. This took a long time intensive process to interpret and ‘fix’ the data sheets.</p> <p>Long-Term Impact: Further research is required to examine the long-term impact</p>
<p>Opportunities</p> <p><i>Highlight areas for potential development, such as refining the methodology, expanding participant demographics, or exploring future research collaborations to enhance insights.</i></p>	<p>Threats</p> <p><i>Identify external challenges that may impact the study’s success, such as resource limitations, data access issues, or potential resistance from stakeholders.</i></p>
<p>Refining the Serious Dilemma Game:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limit the number of persons participants can choose to talk to in the game to avoid participants loss of interest • Move the game to DiBL 2.0 for better game function • Include further information on Green Roof implementation at the beginning of the game. (Case Studies of Best Practices/Videos/Further information on Green Roofs in General) • Update the introduction video to be applicable to all City contexts 	<p>Institutional Resistance: Policymakers and urban planners may be hesitant to adopt games-based consultation methods in traditional planning processes.</p> <p>Financial Constraints: Funding may be a barrier for widespread implementation, particularly if financial assistance for game development or facilitation is not available.</p> <p>Public Perception & Buy-in: Some stakeholders may perceive the game as too</p>

<p>Wider Policy Applications: The methodology can be adapted for other urban planning challenges, such as waste management, mobility, or energy efficiency.</p> <p>Education & Training Integration: Universities and urban planning institutions could integrate game-based learning into curricula.</p> <p>Public Engagement Expansion: The game could be used in broader community consultations and participatory policy development beyond green roofs.</p> <p>Technological Enhancements: Digital or hybrid versions of the game could make it more scalable, interactive, and accessible.</p> <p>Future Research Collaborations: Collaborate with schools and Universities to run the case study/dilemma game both locally and internationally</p>	<p>informal or not serious enough for policy discussions.</p> <p>Adaptation Challenges: Translating the methodology to different cultural, political, or urban contexts may require significant modifications.</p> <p>Stakeholders Time and Budget: This results in limited scope for participation. Enthusiasm does not always mean that policy stakeholders will be able to fully engage in the whole process</p> <p>Level of in Game Participation: During game play itself, leading characters may influence discussions through strong viewpoints. Fortunately this is mitigated by anonymous inputs in to the DiBL game.</p>
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5. Key Findings – Benefits of Rooftop Utilisation

During game sessions, participants identified personal, environmental, and community benefits associated with green rooftop utilization, revealing multifaceted advantages. Environmentally, green rooftops were valued for their ability to improve air quality and regulate climate. Participants also highlighted the sustainability benefits, noting how green rooftops naturally lower energy consumption in summer.

Socially, green rooftops were viewed as creating inviting spaces for community interaction and personal well-being. Many participants saw these rooftops as natural gathering spots where residents could socialize and foster stronger community bonds. They were also seen as peaceful, accessible locations for relaxation, offering views and a reconnection with nature. Additionally, participants valued the potential extra recreational space for activities like yoga, outdoor relaxation, or simply enjoying the city skyline, adding a sense of openness in crowded urban settings.

Lastly, green rooftops were seen to offer critical ecological benefits, supporting biodiversity by creating habitats for insects and bees, thus enriching urban ecosystems. They were viewed as spaces which could increase green spaces in cities, making them accessible to those without private outdoor areas and contributing to local biodiversity and sustainability efforts.

Figure 3. Perceived Benefits of Rooftop Utilization

5.1 Stakeholder Engagement

Throughout the game, participants were invited through an anonymous vote and to choose which stakeholder in a green roof scenario they wanted to engage with first. The voting process highlighted distinct stakeholder priorities, illuminating the perceived importance of each group in the context of green roof initiatives. In the first round, 64% of participants opted to speak with the *'building manager,'* reasoning that the manager, as the individual responsible for building operations, would play a key role in rooftop implementation. This choice underscores the building manager's influence and the need for a strong management role in building operations. Urban planners in later interviews also noted that current building management in Cyprus is underdeveloped and awaits legislative support, which would facilitate such green initiatives. In the second voting round, 69% of participants selected the *'Top Floor Young Couple,'* who had expressed a desire to own part of the roof. Participants reasoned that, given their proximity and vested interest, this couple would be among the most impacted by rooftop changes. Finally, in the third round, 66% of participants chose to engage with *'Parents with Children,'* identifying them as another group with specific needs related to rooftop space use. Notably, *'Senior Citizens'* did not secure enough votes in any session, suggesting that their perspectives were perceived as less directly impacted or adequately understood by participants.

However, feedback from focus groups suggested that participants already recognized the unique challenges faced by older residents in such settings.

This sequence of preferences highlights participants' focus on stakeholders with active or vested interests in rooftop utilization, revealing the priority placed on those who would either manage or directly benefit from green roof initiatives.

5.2 Barriers to Rooftop Utilisation

After engaging with stakeholders, participants identified several pressing barriers to rooftop utilization, with safety, long-term sustainability, and maintenance being the top concerns. These issues reflect a strong focus on ensuring that rooftop spaces are both secure and durable over time. Financial constraints also emerged as a critical barrier, underscoring concerns about the economic feasibility of implementing such projects.

The barriers identified spanned several domains—financial, technical, social, and environmental. Economically, high initial costs, ongoing maintenance expenses, and limited financial support were seen as major challenges. These concerns highlight the need for effective funding mechanisms and incentives to make rooftop greening more accessible, especially for older buildings. In terms of technical and structural issues, participants emphasized the importance of proper planning, including the use of high-quality waterproofing materials and drainage systems to prevent water leakage and structural damage. Additionally, the perceived level of workmanship, particularly in Cyprus, was identified as a significant concern.

Climate considerations were also a key focus, particularly the harsh Cypriot sun. Participants recommended using drought-resistant plants and efficient irrigation systems to maintain green roofs during the long, hot summer months. They also raised concerns about the environmental impact of water usage for rooftop gardens, although solutions like utilizing water lost from air conditioning units were suggested.

Socially, the creation of communal rooftop spaces was seen positively for fostering community interaction and providing recreational areas. However, concerns about privacy for top-floor residents and the need for child-friendly designs also emerged. Disagreements over rooftop management in multi-tenant buildings were identified as another potential obstacle.

On the environmental side, participants pointed to challenges related to climate suitability, water availability, pest control, and air quality. Additionally, concerns about "greenwashing" were raised, with some participants suggesting alternative green infrastructure solutions, such

as planting more trees along streets and creating walkable green spaces, to achieve urban greening without the complexity of rooftop gardens.

The barriers to rooftop utilization identified during the game sessions were multifaceted, with significant challenges across financial, technical, social, and environmental domains. Addressing these issues requires a holistic approach that includes effective funding, technical expertise, careful climate considerations, and community-focused planning.

Figure 4. What is the main barrier to rooftop utilization?

5.3 Incentives for Rooftop Utilization

Participants highlighted financial and maintenance-related support as the most critical incentives for encouraging rooftop utilization. Financial Assistance Programs (23%) emerged as the most preferred incentive, indicating that the high costs associated with implementing and maintaining green rooftops pose a significant barrier. Many participants expressed that direct financial aid, such as grants or subsidies, would make rooftop greening projects more feasible. Similarly, Maintenance Assistance Grants (21%) ranked as the second most important incentive, reflecting concerns about the long-term upkeep of rooftop spaces. Participants emphasized that without proper maintenance support, the sustainability and effectiveness of green rooftops could be compromised.

Beyond financial considerations, safety was another key concern, with Safety Grants (14%). Participants stressed that ensuring rooftops are structurally safe and secure would increase their usability and attractiveness. Additionally, Tenant Engagement Support Programs (14%) were seen as valuable for fostering collaboration among building residents, particularly in multi-tenant buildings where collective decision-making is essential for the successful implementation of rooftop projects.

Figure 5. Incentives for rooftop utilization?

Other incentives received moderate to lower levels of preference. Child-Friendly Design Grants (10%) were particularly relevant for participants who viewed rooftop spaces as potential communal areas that could benefit families. Accessibility was also a recurring concern, with Accessibility Assistance Programs (9%) being chosen by some participants to ensure that rooftop spaces could be designed for inclusivity. Safety Improvement Grants (6%) and Security Upgrades (3%) were selected by fewer participants but still indicated a need for addressing safety and security considerations.

Overall, the data suggests that financial incentives and long-term maintenance support are the primary enablers of rooftop utilization, while safety, accessibility, and community engagement also play important roles in encouraging adoption. These insights highlight the necessity for policymakers to design incentive programs that address both immediate financial barriers and long-term sustainability concerns to maximize the potential of green rooftops.

Overall, the serious dilemma game fostered meaningful discussions by enabling participants to exchange diverse opinions, engage in constructive debates, and gain a deeper understanding of green roofs and urban sustainability. Participants reported that role-playing enhanced empathy, strengthened problem-solving skills, and encouraged collaborative decision-making. The game also facilitated knowledge transfer, allowing individuals from different backgrounds to voice their perspectives and explore innovative urban greening solutions. The innovative methodology utilised in the urban planning context was highlighted during the expert evaluation interviews:

“Bringing the game as a process to discuss big issues like climate change, brings specific solutions. Community engagement as part of the process, is something that is never done in the planning sector.” Marina Kyriakou, Urban Gorillas NGO.

“The GREAT methodology employed brings to the table new voices that would not usually engage in urban planning consultation.” Lora Nicolaou Architect/Urban Planner representative of the president of ETEK, on the Cyprus Town Planning Council.

Facilitators played a key role in engagement, with participants highlighting the importance of interactive and well-structured sessions. The game also demonstrated potential as a policymaking tool, bringing previously unheard voices into urban planning discussions. As noted by Marina Kyriakou from Urban Gorillas, *“Everyone comes from a different position. It's hard to engage with them all at the same time. The game process helps us remove this hierarchy and put things on an even playing field”*.

Policymakers and urban planners recognized its value in community engagement and its adaptability to other policy dilemmas. Despite challenges such as resource intensity and the need for simplification, the game showcased the power of playful participation in driving climate awareness, societal responsibility, and educational impact, particularly in architecture and urban planning.

5.4 Data Gaps

The case study has provided valuable insights into the role of serious games in eliciting and representing citizen perspectives on green rooftop initiatives, yet some gaps remain. First, although participants engaged in discussions about the feasibility of rooftop greening, more structured comparative analysis is needed to measure the effectiveness and efficiency of game-based activities in contrast to traditional consultation methods. More specifically, while qualitative feedback indicates that the game facilitated inclusive participation, there is limited quantitative assessment of how well it represents diverse stakeholder views in decision-making contexts. Further research is also needed to examine the long-term impact of the game-based

approach on participants' attitudes and behaviors beyond the immediate game sessions. Further research may be outside of the scope of the GREAT project, yet working towards these goals will sustain the in-depth methodology built through the project's case studies.

6. Policy Implications and Recommendations

Actionable insights have emerged from the 'Rooftop Revolution' case study as key considerations for successfully implementing a green rooftop policy in Cyprus. These suggestions are designed to inform and guide the development of policies and incentives that will foster the adoption of green rooftops. They emphasize the need for flexible, inclusive, and sustainable approaches to integrating green rooftops into urban environments.

Establish Clear Communication Frameworks Policymakers should mandate the creation of structured communication channels between residents, building managers, and property owners. This will ensure collaborative planning and prevent cost increases linked to maintenance needs and operational challenges of green rooftops.

Ensure Equity and Transparency in Incentive Structures Develop and enforce guidelines for incentives that ensure fairness in the distribution of benefits. Policies should prevent misuse by establishing clear and transparent criteria to guarantee that all stakeholders, including economically disadvantaged residents, have access to the benefits of rooftop greening.

Incentivize Long-Term Sustainability Incentive programs should be structured to reward long-term commitment to sustainability. Policies should prioritize green roofs that offer lasting environmental and economic benefits, ensuring that such projects continue to support climate resilience and energy efficiency over time.

Provide Financial Support for Disadvantaged Residents Implement financial mechanisms, such as subsidies, rent discounts, or reductions in common expenses, to make green rooftops more accessible to low-income residents. This will ensure that rooftop greening initiatives are inclusive and do not exacerbate existing social inequalities.

Support Market Differentiation Through Green Certifications Encourage property owners to invest in green rooftop solutions by offering incentives for obtaining 'green building' certifications. These certifications should be linked to increased property value, making sustainable building practices more appealing to investors and developers.

Invest in Skill Development and Capacity Building Policymakers should allocate resources for targeted training and skill development programs for building managers, architects, developers,

and other relevant stakeholders. This will ensure that those responsible for green roof implementation have the necessary expertise to execute and maintain these systems effectively.

Adopt Flexible Policies for Varied Building Types Recognize the diversity of building types and economic contexts by adopting flexible policies that accommodate the unique needs of older buildings and properties with different financial capabilities. This approach will allow green rooftop projects to be scaled and adapted to a variety of urban settings.

Provide Evidence and Data Policymakers should ensure that architects, developers, and property owners have access to comprehensive data on the benefits and costs of green roofs. Providing quantitative evidence on energy savings, environmental benefits, and cost reductions will facilitate informed decision-making and encourage wider adoption.

Extended Warranty Periods for Green Roof Installations Policies should incentivize green roof installations by offering extended warranty periods. This reduces the perceived risk for property owners and makes green roofs a more attractive investment by ensuring long-term durability and performance.

Implement Clear Resident Agreements Establish policies that require residents to enter into formal agreements regarding the responsibilities and benefits of maintaining green roofs, similar to those for photovoltaic (PV) panel installations. This will clarify expectations and encourage greater resident participation in rooftop projects.

Anticipate Diverse Developer Responses: To foster collaboration and support, it is essential to emphasize the potential advantages of green roofs, including increased property value, enhanced corporate social responsibility (CSR) opportunities, and marketing benefits that developers can leverage to strengthen their portfolios and appeal to eco-conscious consumers.

These policy insights outline actionable steps for local and national governments to promote the widespread adoption of green rooftops. The key focus areas include incentivizing sustainability, providing financial support for disadvantaged residents, ensuring fair and transparent policies, and supporting education and training for all involved stakeholders. By addressing the technical, social, and financial barriers to green roof implementation, policymakers can significantly advance the environmental and economic benefits of green rooftops while fostering social inclusion.

7. Conclusion

The ‘Rooftops Reimagined’ case study has demonstrated the potential of serious games in urban planning, climate change education, and participatory decision-making. By integrating the GREAT approach, the initiative provided an innovative platform for diverse stakeholders including: citizens; students; policymakers; and urban planners. As a result these groups have collaboratively explored the challenges and opportunities of green rooftops and methods to incentivize their implementation. This case study has highlighted how game-based methodologies have the potential to bridge the gap between communities and decision-makers, fostering inclusive dialogue and actionable insights on sustainable urban development, especially when discussing environmental or climate change initiatives.

Participants found the game straightforward with guidance but noted that without expert assistance, the game might have been confusing. The game facilitated diverse opinions and constructive disagreements, enhancing realism. Key issues discussed included the need for better building management, the importance of accessibility, and the challenges of maintenance and financial constraints. Socially, the study underscored the value of community engagement in shared rooftop projects, identifying both opportunities for fostering social interaction and challenges related to accessibility and privacy. Environmentally, green rooftops were widely recognized for their potential to enhance air quality, reduce urban heat island effects, and increase biodiversity—provided that implementation strategies account for regional climate conditions and water availability.

Key Takeaways:

- **Serious Games as a Consultation Tool:** The game-based approach facilitated dynamic discussions, making complex urban planning issues more accessible and inclusive.
- **Financial & Technical Barriers:** High costs, maintenance challenges, and structural considerations were identified as key constraints requiring policy interventions.
- **Community Engagement & Social Dynamics:** Collaborative decision-making among residents, building managers, and developers is crucial for successful rooftop projects.
- **Environmental & Policy Implications:** Green rooftops offer multiple benefits, but their effectiveness depends on strategic implementation, policy support, and incentive structures.

The success of Rooftops Reimagined opens pathways for further research and practical applications:

- **Scaling & Policy Adaptation:** Expanding the methodology to other environmental and urban planning challenges, such as waste management and renewable energy policies.
- **Integration into Design Education:** Enhancing its role as a learning tool for architecture, urban planning, and environmental studies.
- **Long-Term Impact Assessment:** Measuring behavioral changes and policy shifts influenced by participatory game sessions.

Referring back to the GREAT projects Research Questions the study explored a serious dilemma game which encompassed role-playing and interactive decision making to engage participants. This approach allowed stakeholders to negotiate and voice opinions, this makes it an example of how games-based activities can be used to elicit, represent, and communicate citizens' views on social dilemmas (RQ1.1). The case study findings further suggest that the methodology enhanced discussions and provided diverse perspectives and participatory problem solving throughout the game. Findings also showed that role-playing elements allowed participants to empathise with various viewpoints, post-session feedback indicated that participants all felt equally heard, thus showing that the serious dilemma game was effective in eliciting, representing, and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas (RQ1.2). Furthermore in relevance to RQ1.2, participants themselves provided a number of ideas and further perspectives to the dilemma presented to them, allowing for two-way knowledge transfer.

Feedback from experts highlighted that the game-based methodology facilitated an inclusive dialogue, yet the time required, need for facilitator training and the complexity of the game design itself may impact negatively on how efficient is the use of games-based activities in eliciting, representing, and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas (RQ1.3), the efficiency of the game would depend on the future ability to simplify and scale the games-based model.

Lastly in relation to the affordances of games in eliciting and representing citizens' views in relation to social dilemmas (RQ2.1), the 'Rooftop Revolution' case study:

- Encouraged Participation
- Facilitated role-changing and perspective-taking, thus fostering empathy
- Supported structured yet creative problem-solving in policy engagement
- Bridged the gap between citizens and policymakers in a novel way

'Rooftop Revolution' highlights using serious games as a bridge between education, policy, and community-driven climate action. The insights gathered aim to inform future policies, and

best practices, ultimately advancing the wider adoption of green infrastructure in urban environments.

8. References

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